

**ANALYSIS OF WILLIAM FAULKNER'S WORLD VIEW IN A
ROSE FOR EMILY
(STUDY OF LUCIEN GOLDMANN'S GENETIC
STRUCTURALISM) by Kahar Dwi Prihantono**

Braydon Young
Aquaculture-IPB University
braydon0606@gmail.com

Abstract

This study aims to gain an understanding of William Faulkner's world view in the short story "A Rose for Emily" (*ArfE*). This research uses a dialectical method with a genetic structuralism approach. The problems discussed include (1) the structure of the short story; (2) William Faulkner's worldview; (3) social structure, and social groups represented by the author. Research data in the form of sentences or paragraphs, dialogues, and monologues contained in the short story *ArfE* by William Faulkner. Based on the analysis of the structure of the short story, the writer finds the relation between cultural opposition, social opposition, natural opposition, and human opposition.

Keywords: *genetic structuralism; A Rose for Emily; social structure; world view*

INTRODUCTION

The short story "A Rose for Emily" (*ArfE*) reveals the struggles of southern individuals in the midst of the southern economic decline in the late 1860s. Miss Emily is the last descendant of the Griersons family who is steadfast against change. This study uses a genetic structuralism approach to analyze the short story *A Rose for Emily* (*ArfE*) because the researcher is interested in seeing how Faulkner's world view is based on his social background and the social background of southern society in the short story. Writer interested use approach structuralism genetics for know view world Faulkner which use

literature for convey aspirations and her feelings about inequality level humans in America.

There are several similar studies that look at the same material object, the short story *ARfE*. Some examples include a study entitled *Symbols in William Faulkner's Short Story "Arose for Emily": A Semiotic Approach* written by Eka Wilany. Similar studies using the genetic structuralism approach have been carried out by several researchers. However, the author believes that this research is more interesting because it involves a very long story setting (approximately 74 years) and a social setting that has undergone changes during that time. There are four main problems that become the focus of this research, namely (a) how is the structure of the *ARfE short story*, (b) what kind of social structure exists in Southern society and the *ARfE short story*, (c) what kind of world view is present as a representation of William Faulkner, and (d) what social group does William Faulkner represent.

METHOD

This study of analysis uses a descriptive qualitative method because it explains a social event for how the writer uses for analyzing the paper. This method is seen by the writer to be very important because this method will show a form of explanation related to a phenomenon that is interpreted in the context and concept of writing. Of course, in carrying out this research, the author uses a hermeneutic approach because this paper analysis will be studied by exegesis of the contents and adjusting to the events that occurred at that time. The analysis of this research uses the theoretical framework that exists in Lucien's genetic-structuralism Goldmann, namely the dialectical method. Meanwhile, data collection was carried out in three ways, namely (1) observation by looking for *ARfE short stories*, (2) documentation by reading short stories, and (3) literature study by reading some literature that supports and becomes a research reference. The data collection method used is the library method. The material taken as the object of research is in the form of literary texts and other texts related to the object of research.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings in this study are in the short story *ARfE*, Faulkner does not use a general approach in describing the life span of a character. The illustration also makes it easier for the author to examine the structure of the short story, world view, and social structure. The era of reconstruction marked by optimizing the collection of taxes to southern communities as shown by federal instructions in the short story. The society of Jefferson City after *Civil War* is described

by Faulkner as a social, caring, obedient, open, caring, obedient, open, modern, communal, humanist society in contrast to Miss Emily who is a former upper class citizen of pre - *Civil War* who is antisocial , indifferent, ignorant, closed, conservative/traditional, individual, and inhumane. The humans in ArfE 's short stories and those studied by the author include the narrator (city residents), Colonel Sartoris , Mr. Grierson , Miss Emily, Homer Baron, Judge Steven, and Tobe. The new mayor and a new generation of Jefferson City Council began to oppose the policies of the old mayor, Colonel Sartoris , which exempted taxes for the aristocratic family, the Griersons .

The purpose of a this analysis of papers in the form of discussions are Miss Emily refusing to pay the tax bill in the new generation of government. He maintained that in 1894 the old mayor, Colonel Sartoris , granted him a tax exemption after his father died. Emily told the tax man to look at the photo of the old mayor, Colonel Sartoris , that was hanging on the wall of his house when the tax man came ten years after his father's death. The Griersons were known to the townspeople as an aristocratic family. Emily's father was a Confederate soldier who participated in the *Civil War*. This family is known to be very strict in maintaining the association of their daughters. The same thing happened to Emily. Emily's father considered that there was no man in the city who was considered worthy to be his companion. The summer after Emily's father's death, northern worker Homer Baron comes to build sidewalks until he finally hooks up with Miss Emily . At first the town women believed that Miss Emily would not like the northern workers.

CONCLUSION

For how the writer subjectively see from the paper analysis that Several important figures in this research, namely Miss Emily, the townspeople, Homer Baron, and Tobe. The structure of literary works expresses a modern and humanist worldview. Through the character of the townspeople (as a narrator) William Faulkner indirectly strongly rejects the conservation of *Old South values* because it is contrary to ideal human values, as the glorification of aristocratic social status in the past is no longer in accordance with the times. This short story was written around 1929 (this can be seen from *note* or notes written by William Faulkner in 1929 he bought the *antebellum house* or the big house left by the *gentry family* who had slumped during the *New South* which became the idea of writing this short story), the social structure of southern society is being hit by bankruptcy due to the *Civil War* and society is struggling in the reconstruction era until the *Great Depression era* . By using the dialectical method, the writer finds that the short story expresses the world view that is believed to be in the environment of certain social characters. This view is modern humanism.

REFERENCES

- Altman, R. (2021). 3. A Semantic/Syntactic Approach to genre films. In *Film genre reader IV* (pp. 27-41). University of Texas Press.
- Barus , IRG, Simanjuntak , MB, & Resmayasari , I. (2021). READING LITERACIES THROUGH EVIETA-BASED LEARNING MATERIAL: STUDENTS'PERCEPTIONS (Study Case Taken from Vocational School–IPB University). *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES* , 4 (1), 15-20.
- Bateman, J., & Schmidt, KH (2013). *Multimodal film analysis: How films mean* . Routledge.
- Bednarek , M. (2015). Corpus-assisted multimodal discourse analysis of television and film narratives. In *Corpora and discourse studies* (pp. 63-87). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- Bellour , R. (2000). *The analysis of films* . Indiana University Press.
- Benshoff , H. (2015). *Film and television analysis: An introduction to methods, theories, and approaches* . Routledge.
- Bernadtua , M., Rafli , Z., & Boeriswati , E. (2022, January). LANGUAGES ACQUISITION AND TEACHING IN KELAPA GADING–NORTH JAKARTA (CASE STUDY TAKEN AT SAINT PETER'S JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL). In *UICELL Conference Proceedings* (pp. 162-170).
- Bittau , F., Potamialis , C., Togay , M., Abbas, A., Isherwood, PJ, Bowers, JW, & Walls, JM (2018). Analysis and optimization of the glass/TCO/MZO stack for thin film CdTe solar cells. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* , 187 , 15-22.
- Carr, D. (2019). Methodology, representation, and games. *Games and Culture* , 14 (7-8), 707-723.
- Condon, WS, & Ogston , WD (1966). Sound film analysis of normal and pathological behavior patterns. *Journal of nervous and mental diseases* .
- Estrada, LM, Hielscher, E., Koolen , M., Olesen, CG, Noordegraaf , J., & Blom , J. (2017). Film analysis as annotation: Exploring current tools. *Moving Image: The Journal of the Association of Moving Image Archivists* , 17 (2), 40-70.
- Franco, A., Magnani, A., & Maio, D. (2020). A multimodal approach for human activity recognition based on skeleton and RGB data. *Pattern Recognition Letters* , 131 , 293-299.
- Geiger, J., & Rutsky , RL (Eds.). (2013). *Film analysis: A Norton reader* . WW Norton & Company.
- Henseler , C. (2021). Finding Humanity. *The Scholar as Human: Research and Teaching for Public Impact* , 129.
- Jahn, M. (2003). A guide to narrative film analysis. *Poems, Plays, and Prose: A Guide to the Theory of Literary Genres* , 2 .
- Kendrick, M. (2016). *Literacy and multimodality across global sites* . Routledge.
- Kozlarek , O. (2015). Introduction: Crossing Borders, Reaching Humanity. In *Octavio Paz* (pp. 9-16). transcript-Verlag.

- Liu, AA, Xu, N., Nie , WZ, Su, YT, Wong, Y., & Kankanhalli , M. (2016). Benchmarking a multimodal and multiview and interactive dataset for human action recognition. *IEEE Transactions on cybernetics* , 47 (7), 1781-1794.
- Lo, HF, Wu, IW, & Ni, CC (2018, July). Representation of Memory in Design for Humanity. In *International Conference on Cross-Cultural Design* (pp. 43-57). Springer, Cham.
- Magnusson, P., & Godhe , AL (2019). Multimodality in Language Education--Implications for Teaching. *Designs for Learning* , 11 (1), 127-137.
- Parc, J. (2018). Evaluating the effects of protectionism on the film industry: A case study analysis of Korea. In *Handbook of State Aid for Film* (pp. 349-366). Springer, Cham.
- Pattiwael , AS (2019). Literature for Developing Student's Humanity Awareness. In *Journal International Seminar on Languages, Literature, Arts, and Education (ISLLAE)* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 79-88).
- Peña-Cervel , MS (2016). Motivating film title translation: a cognitive analysis. *CRCULO de Linguística Aplicada a la Comunicación* , 66 , 31.
- Plate, L. (2015). How to do things with literature in the digital age: Anne Carson's Nox , multimodality, and the ethics of bookishness. *Contemporary Women's Writing* , 9 (1), 93-111.
- Richards, M. (2016). Film Music Themes: Analysis and Corpus Study. *Music Theory Online* , 22 (1).
- Rosenberg, FJ (2016). *After Human Rights: Literature, Visual Arts, and Film in Latin America, 1990-2010* . University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Rouast , PV, Adam, MT, & Chiong , R. (2019). Deep learning for human affect recognition: Insights and new developments. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* , 12 (2), 524-543.
- Santos, RB, & de Oliveira, UR (2019). Analysis of occupational risk management tools for the film and television industry. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics* , 72 , 199-211.
- Serafini, F. (2015). Multimodal literacy: From theories to practices. *Language Arts* , 92 (6), 412-423.
- Simanjuntak , MB (2021). METAMORPHIC ANALYSIS IN SONG LYRICS BATAK TOBA “AUT BOI NIAN” WRITTEN BY WERVIN PANGGABEAN. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES* , 4 (1), 34-39.
- Simanjuntak , MB., Suseno , M., Ramdhoni , R., Mayuni , I., Zuriyati , Z., & Sutrisno , S. (2022). The Value of Parents' Image in Seven Batak Toba Songs (Literary Art Study). *Tambusai Journal of Education* , 6 (2), 8540–8551.
- Simanjuntak , MB, & Barus , IRG (2020). English Reading Literacies to Improve Values Among Teenagers. *SELTICS* , 93-102.
- Simanjuntak , MB, & Lumingkewas , MS (2022, January). THE WOMAN IN THE BOOK OF KINGS (LITERARY STUDIES AND HERMENEUTICS). In *UICELL Conference Proceeding* (pp. 328-334).

- Simanjuntak , MB, Barus , IRG, & Resmayasari , I. (2021). ANALYSIS OF VIOLENCE IN CITY OF GOD FILM DIRECTED BY FERNANDO MEIRELLES. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES* , 4 (1), 1-6.
- Simanjuntak , MB, Barus , IRG, & Resmayasari , I. (2021, January). Analysis of Song" My Hands Na Metmet " by Using Translation Techniques into English. In *UICELL Conference Proceeding* (pp. 195-202).
- Simanjuntak , MB, Lumingkewas , MS, & Sutrisno , S. (2021). ANALYSIS OF TANGIANG ALE AMANAMI (OUR FATHER) USING THE TECHNIQUES OF TRANSLATION. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES* , 4 (2), 70-75.
- Simanjuntak , MB, Rahmat , A. . , Setiadi , S. . , Suseno , M. . , Romdani , R., & Lumingkewas , MS . (2022). Power Relations in the Story of “ Nommensen Meeting King Panggalamei ” by Patar Pasaribu . *Tambusai Journal of Education* , 6 (2), 8552–8557.
- Simanjuntak , MB, Suseno , M., & Setiadi , S. (2022, January). THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MICROSOFT OFFICE 365 AS AN ONLINE ENGLISH LEARNING MEDIA. In *UICELL Conference Proceedings* (pp. 25-32).
- Simanjuntak , MB, Suseno , M., Setiadi , S., Lustyantie , N., & Barus , IRGRG (2022). Integration of Curricula (Curriculum 2013 and Cambridge Curriculum for Junior High School Level in Three Subjects) in Pandemic Situation. *Ideas: Journal of Education, Social , and Culture* , 8 (1), 77-86.
- Simanjuntak , MB, Sutrisno , S., & Lumingkewas , MS (2021). LITERARY STUDY “NOMMENSEN, APOSTLE IN BATAKNESE”. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES* , 4 (2), 42-45.
- Simanjuntak , MB, Zuriyati , Z., & Lustyantie , N. (2022). METAMORPHIC ANALYSIS IN SONG LYRICS BATAK TOBA “JUJUNG GOARHI AMANG ”(STUDY OF PORTRAY OF PARENTS). *PROJECT (Professional Journal of English Education)* , 5 (1), 236-243.
- Simanjuntak , MB, Zuriyati , Z., Utami , SR, & Lumingkewas , MS (2022). Nommensen and Bataknese (The Representation of Apostle). *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal): Humanities and Social Sciences* , 5 (2), 9291-9297.
- Sleman, SM, & Fahmi, IM (2020). The Destiny of Humanity in the Future Cities of Ray Bradbury. *Zanco Journal of Humanity Sciences* , 24 (1), 278-288.
- Teixeira, MBM, da Costa Galvao , LL, Mota -Santos, CM, & Carmo , LJO (2020). Women and work: film analysis of Most Beautiful Thing. *Revista de Gestão* .
- Way, LC, & McKerrell , S. (Eds.). (2017). *Music as multimodal discourse: Semiotics, power and protest* . Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Wellek , R. (2018). *The attack on literature and other essays* . UNC Press Books.
- Widjayanti , EP (2019). Building Humanity Values Through Maya Angelou's poems. In *Journal International Seminar on Languages, Literature, Arts, and Education (ISLLAE)* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 143-148).

Wildfeuer , J. (2014). *Film discourse interpretation: Towards a new paradigm for multimodal film analysis* . Routledge.

Wu, J., & Yan, Y. (2016, November). Study of humanity teaching model in higher vocational school Chinese teaching. In *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Management Science, Education Technology , Arts, Social Science and Economics* (Vol. 85, pp. 1855-1858).

